

Use of Potassium Bromate : Bromination of Benzene

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Bromination of benzene using potassium bromate as the brominating agent has been studied under various conditions.

THE observation¹ that potassium bromate under acidic condition was a unique brominating agent for aromatic acids prompted us to study the bromination of the aromatic hydrocarbons using this reagent taking benzene as the pilot compound. It has been observed that benzene can be brominated to a mixture of bromobenzene and 1,4-dibromobenzene using excess of potassium bromate in moderately strong sulphuric acid. But only bromobenzene was obtained to the extent of 70% when a mixture of pure glacial acetic and 8-4(N) sulphuric acids were used under similar experimental conditions which also suggested that one molar equivalent of potassium bromate was consumed there. The identity of the bromination product, b.p. 153-155°, was established through the identical I.R. spectra of the authentic bromobenzene and the product. It has been further observed that nascent bromine and elemental bromine could produce less than 15% and 10% bromobenzene respectively. When bromobenzene was used as the starting material, 1,4-dibromobenzene², m.p. 87-88°, was obtained in 20% yield using potassium bromate in conjunction with 8-4(N) sulphuric acid under refluxing condition for one and a half hours, but when a mixture of pure acetic and 8-4(N) sulphuric acids were used the yield of the desired product rose up to 40% under similar conditions. The identity of the product as 1,4-dibromobenzene, m.p. 87-88°, was established through I.R., N. M. R. and Mass spectra of the compound. Potassium bromate could not brominate either benzene or bromobenzene when used with acetic acid alone. Other aromatic hydrocarbons, halobenzenes, aromatic ethers and heterocyclic compounds are under investigations.

Experimental

A. R. acetic acid was heated under reflux with excess of potassium dichromate for six hours and distilled just before use. Pure potassium bromate, sulphuric acid and distilled water were used whenever needed.

1(a) Bromination of Benzene with Potassium Bromate in 8-4(N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzene (16.0 g) and sulphuric acid (8N; 150 ml) was heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate (prepared by dissolving 16.7 g of potassium bromate in 150 ml of warm distilled water) was added dropwise from the separating funnel in course of thirty minutes. The refluxing was continued for further one hour. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto iced-water followed by the extraction with ether. The organic layer was washed successively with water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, distilled water and dried over sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a residue was obtained which was distilled to furnish a colourless oil with characteristic smell, b.p. 153-155° (10.2 g; 70%). The high boiling dark solid residue (approx. 2.0 g), left in the distilling flask, was treated with activated charcoal and crystallised from ethanol to furnish colourless flakes (0.5 g) m.p. 87°, which was characterised to be 1,4-dibromobenzene. The I.R. spectra of the product, b.p. 153-155° and authentic bromobenzene (ν_{max} 3050, 1580, 1470, 1440, 1056, 1018, 728, 680 and 669 cm^{-1}) were identical in all respects.

The I.R. spectrum of the compound, m.p. 87°, exhibited the following peaks : (ν_{Nujol} 1455, 1373, 1068, 1008 and 812 cm^{-1}). Anal. Found C, 30.72%, H, 2.0%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br}_2$; C, 30.51%; H, 1.69%. Mass spectra, m/e 234 (M^+), m/e 155 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Br}$) and n.m.r., $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$, 7.38 (s) ppm³.

(b) Bromination of Benzene with Potassium Bromate in a Mixture of Glacial Acetic Acid and 8-4(N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzene (27.0 ml), acetic acid (200 ml) and sulphuric acid (8N; 150 ml) was

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heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate (16.7 g in 150 ml of water) was added dropwise from the separating funnel in course of thirty minutes. It was noted that immediately after the addition of a few drops of potassium bromate solution the reaction mixture turned red which faded to light yellow at the end of the reaction lasting for one and a half hours. No odour of elemental bromine was perceptible and a gas was collected by displacement of dilute alkali which was found to be oxygen. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto iced-water followed by the extraction with chloroform and worked up to furnish a liquid which distilled to yield a colourless oil (10.2 g ; 70%), b.p. 154-155°, characterised as bromobenzene.

(c) Bromination of Benzene with Excess of Potassium Bromate in 8 (N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzene (8.0 g) and sulphuric acid (8N ; 300 ml) was heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate (41.0 g in 300 ml of water) was added dropwise in course of thirty minutes. During the progress of the reaction a brown liquid refluxed and a heavy yellow oil settled down after one and a half hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto iced-water and extracted as usual with ether and distilled to furnish a liquid (0.85g), b.p. 75-78°/54 mm, and a gummy solid (9.40 g), b.p. 129-134°/54 mm. The latter on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished colourless flakes (2.0 g), m.p. 87°, and characterised as 1,4-dibromobenzene. Mother liquor yielded an oil which was not further investigated.

(d) Attempted Bromination of Benzene with Potassium Bromate in Glacial Acetic Acid :

A mixture of benzene (27.0 ml), acetic acid (100 ml), water (10 ml) and potassium bromate (16.7 g) was refluxed for one and a half hours. The mixture was worked up with chloroform in the usual way and removal of the solvent on steambath yielded no reaction product.

(e) Bromination of Benzene with a Mixture of Potassium Bromate, Potassium Bromide and 8 (N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzene (20.0 ml) and sulphuric acid (8N ; 100 ml) was heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate-bromide (potassium bromide, 25.6 g and potassium bromate, 5.12g, in 64 ml of warm water) was added dropwise within a period of twenty minutes and refluxing was continued for further one hour. Excess of bromine was destroyed by formic acid and the reaction mixture was worked up with ether to furnish bromobenzene (2.0 g ; 13%), b.p. 153-154°.

(f) Bromination of Benzene with Elemental Bromine in 8 (N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzene (20.0 ml), sulphuric acid (8N ; 100 ml) and bromine (liquid ; 4.5 ml) was heated under reflux for one and a half hours. Excess of bromine was decomposed by formic acid and the reaction mixture was worked up with ether to furnish bromobenzene (1.3 g ; 8%), b.p. 153-154°.

2(a) Bromination of Bromobenzene with Potassium Bromate in 8 (N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of bromobenzene (16.0 g) and sulphuric acid (8N ; 115 ml) was heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate (8.5g in 115 ml of water) was added dropwise within a period of thirty minutes. After refluxing for another hour the reaction mixture was cooled and worked up in the usual way with ether. Removal of the solvent furnished a yellowish brown oil (17.7 g) which on distillation furnished recovered bromobenzene (13.6 g), b.p. 130-135°/water aspirator, and a yellow gummy solid (5.1 g ; 45%), b.p. 190-195°/water aspirator. The latter on crystallisation from ethanol yielded colourless flakes (2.3 g ; 20%), m.p. 87°, which was identified as 1,4-dibromobenzene.

(b) Bromination of Bromobenzene with Potassium Bromate in Glacial Acetic Acid and 8(N) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of bromobenzene (31.4 g), acetic acid (350 ml) and sulphuric acid (8N ; 150 ml) was heated under reflux and a solution of potassium bromate (16.7 g in 150 ml of water) was added in course of thirty minutes. Initial pink reaction mixture became light yellow towards the end of another hour of refluxing. The reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with chloroform in the usual way. Removal of the solvent and distillation of the residue yielded a yellow gummy solid (17.6g ; approx. 75%), b.p. 200-206°/water aspirator, together with the unreacted bromobenzene (16.1 g). The gummy solid on crystallisation from ethanol yielded pure 1,4-dibromobenzene (9.0 g, m.p. 87°, 40%). The mother liquor on concentration yielded an oil (8.0 g) which is under further investigation for the possible presence of 1,2-dibromobenzene.

(c) Attempted Bromination of Bromobenzene with Potassium Bromate in Glacial Acetic Acid :

To a refluxing mixture of bromobenzene (30.7 g) and glacial acetic acid (200 ml) was added dropwise a solution of potassium bromate (16.7 g) in warm water (150 ml) in course of thirty minutes. An initial intense red colour soon faded away and the solution was refluxed for one and a half hours. The mixture was worked up with chloroform as usual. Removal of the solvent and distillation of

the residue furnished the unreacted bromobenzene (28.0 g), b.p. 153-155°. The residue in the distillation flask (Ca. 0.5 g) on crystallisation from ethanol, furnished traces of 1,4-dibromobenzene, m.p. 87°.

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